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Neurobehavioral conditions and effects of gender, weight and severity in preterm infants according to the Neonatal Behavioral Assessment Scale

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6018/analesps.31.3.170181>**Keywords:** Neonatal Behavioral Assessment Scale, NBAS, prematurity, neonatal neurobehavior, neonatal development assessment**Abstract**

The increasing number of preterm babies in recent years has raised interest in studying the consequences of prematurity as a risk factor. In the present paper, 30 preterm babies (at 40 weeks of gestational age (GA)) were assessed using the Neonatal Behavioral Assessment Scale and the results were compared with those of a control group of 28 full term babies. Moreover, the influence of weight, sex and GA was analyzed considering the Brazelton results in the preterm group.

The preterm group showed significantly lower scores than the control group for 9 of the 28 behavioral items in the Scale and for 2 of the 5 clusters. However, preterm babies performed better in habituation to disturbing stimuli (light and sound) during sleep. In relation to the influence of sex, premature girls performed better in the Social-Interactive cluster.

The preterm group has lower neurobehavioral conditions than the full term group, probably due to the abrupt interruption of their intrauterine maturation. In contrast, they showed a better ability of habituation, maybe as a consequence of a learning effect due to earlier additional extrauterine exposition.

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References

Bisiacchi, P.S., Mento, G., Suppiej, A. (2009) Cortical auditory processing in preterm newborns: an ERP study. *Biological Psychology*, 82 (2), 176-185.

Brazelton, T. & Nugent, B. (1997) *Escala para la Evaluación del Comportamiento Neonatal*, 3ª Ed., España: Paidós Iberica.

Brazelton, T. & Nugent, B. (2011) *Neonatal Behavioral Assessment Scale*, 4th Ed., Hoboken, NJ US: John Wiley & Sons Inc.

Boatella-Costa, E., Costas-Moragas, C., Botet-Mussons, F., Fornieles-Deu, A., & De Cáceres-Zurita ML. (2007). Behavioral gender differences in the neonatal period according to the Brazelton scale. *Early Human Development*, 83 (2), 91-97.

Canals, J., Fernández-Ballart, J., & Esparó, G. (2003). Evolution of neonatal behavior assessment scale scores in the first month life. *Infant Behavior & Development*, 26 (2), 227-237.

Cloherly, J., Eichenwald, E., Stark, A. (2005). *Manual de cuidados neonatales*, 4ª Ed., España: Massons.

Costas-Moragas, C. (2009). Perinatal factors influencing development: Spain. En K. J. Nugent, B. J. Petrauskas, T. B. Brazelton, K. J. Nugent, B. J. Petrauskas & T. B. Brazelton (Eds.), *The newborn as a person: Enabling healthy infant development worldwide*. (pp. 41-50). Hoboken, NJ US: John Wiley & Sons Inc.

Costas-Moragas, C., Fornieles-Deu, A., Botet-Mussons, F., Boatella-Costa, E., & de Cáceres Zurita, M. L. (2007). Evaluación psicométrica de la escala de brazelton en una muestra de recién nacidos españoles. *Psicothema*, 19 (1), 140-149.

Davis, N. M., Ford, G. W., Anderson, P. J., Doyle, L. W., & Victorian Infant Collaborative Study Group. (2007). Developmental coordination disorder at 8 years of age in a regional cohort of extremely-low-birthweight or very preterm infants. *Developmental Medicine and Child Neurology*, 49 (5), 325-330.

Feldman, R. & Eidelman, Al. (2003) Skin-to-skin contact (Kangaroo Care) accelerates autonomic and neurobehavioural maturation in preterm infants. *Developmental medicine and child neurology*, 45 (4),

274-281.

Figueras, F., Meler, E., Iraola, A., Eixarch, E., Coll, O., Figueras, J., et al. (2008). Customized birthweight standards for a spanish population. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 136(1), 20-24.

Figueras, F., Oros, D., Cruz-Martinez, R., Padilla, N., Hernandez-Andrade, E., Botet, F., Costas-Moragas, C., & Gratacos, E. (2009) Neurobehavior in Term, Small-for-Gestational Age Infants With Normal Placental Function. *Pediatrics*, 124, e934-e941. doi: 10.1542/peds.2008-3346

Forcada, M., Muller-Nix, C., Fumeaux, P., Pierrehumbert, B., Moessinger, A. & Ansermet, F. (2000). Neonatal behavior and parental representations of the preterm infant. *Infant Mental Health Journal*, 4-5 (Special Issue) 7th Congress World Association for Infant Mental Health. Abstract n.111.

Grunau, R.E. (2006). Long-term consequences of pain in human neonates. *Seminars in Fetal&Neonatal Medicine*, 11 (4), 268-275.

IBM SPSS Inc. M.J. Norusis (2011): *IBM SPSS Statistics 19 Guide to Data Analysis*. Chicago: SPSS INC.

Instituto Nacional de Estadística (2010, May 10). Madrid:

INE

Retrieved April 28, 2012, from <http://www.ine.es/jaxi/tabla.do?type=pcaxis&path=/t20/e301/nacim/a2008/10/&file=01010.px>

Jiménez, R., Figueras, J., Villanueva, C. & Botet F. (1982) Valoración del crecimiento intrauterino a nivel del mar, entre las 25 y 43 semanas de edad gestacional. *Archivos de Pediatría*, 33, 191-200.

Kelly, S.J., Ostrowski, N.L. & Wilson, M.A. (1999) Gender differences in brain and behavior: hormonal and neural bases. *Pharmacology Biochemistry and Behavior*, 64, 655-664.

Limperopoulos, C., Bassan, H., Sullivan, N. R., Soul, J. S., Robertson, R. L., Jr, Moore, M., et al. (2008). Positive screening for autism in ex-preterm infants: Prevalence and risk factors. *Pediatrics*, 121(4), 758-765.

Lundqvist, C., & Sabel, K. (2000). Brief report: The brazelton neonatal behavioral assessment scale detects differences among newborn infants of optimal health. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, 25(8), 577-582.

Newsham, D., Knox, P. C., & Cooke, R. W. (2007). Oculomotor control in children who were born very prematurely. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science*, 48(6), 2595-2601.

Nugent, K., Petrauskas, B. & Brazelton T. (2009). The newborn as a person: Enabling healthy infant development worldwide. Hoboken, NJ US: John Wiley & Sons Inc.

Ohgi, S., Arisawa, K., Takahashi, T., Kusumoto, T., Goto, Y., Akiyama, T., et al. (2003). Neonatal behavioral assessment scale as a predictor of later developmental disabilities of low birth-weight and/or premature infants. *Brain & Development*, 25(5), 313-321.

Rao, R., Sampers, J. S., Kronsberg, S. S., Brown, J. V., Desai, N. S., & Anand, K. J. (2007). Neurobehavior of preterm infants at 36 weeks postconception as a function of morphine analgesia. *American Journal of Perinatology*, 24(9), 511-517.

Seme-Ciglenecki, P. (2007). Predictive values of cranial ultrasound and assessment of general movements for neurological development of preterm infants in the maribor region of slovenia. *Wiener Klinische Wochenschrift*, 119(15-16), 490-496.

Spinillo, A., Montanari, L., Gardella, B., Roccio, M., Stronati, M., & Fazzi, E. (2009). Infant sex, obstetric risk factors, and 2-year neurodevelopmental outcome among preterm infants. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, 51(7), 518-525.

Soria-Pastor, S., Padilla, N., Zubiaurre-Elorza, L., Ibarretxe-Bilbao, N., Botet, F., Costas-Moragas, C., Falcon, C., Bargallo, N., Mercader, JM., & Junqué, C. (2009). Decreased Regional Brain Volume and Cognitive Impairment in Preterm Children at Low Risk. *Pediatrics*, 124, e1161-e1170. doi: 10.1542/peds.2009-0244

Valero de Bernabé, J., Soriano, T., Albaladejo, R., Juarranz, M., Calle, M. E., Martínez, D., et al. (2004). Risk factors for low birth weight: A review. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 116(1), 3-15.

Woodward, L. J., Anderson, P. J., Austin, N. C., Howard, K., e Inder, T. E. (2006). Neonatal MRI to predict neurodevelopmental outcomes in preterm infants. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 355(7), 685-694.

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